

ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION AS A SOCIO- PEDAGOGICAL AND HYGIENIC PROBLEM

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Abstract. *Ecological knowledge considers society and nature in their interaction. Social sciences reveal the goals that a person pursues, using nature, give a description of the values that a person relies on or should rely on in his activities. Formation of environmental value orientations. Environmental education includes students' awareness of the diverse value of nature as a source of meeting the diverse needs of society as a whole and each individual. A system of norms and rules of attitude to nature. While studying the basics of science, the student should be aware of the social and natural causes that dictate certain norms and rules of professional and individual behavior in the environment.*

Keywords: *environmental, education. social and pedagogical, hygienic, problem, source.*

Relevance. Compliance with these norms and rules is a socially necessary act that allows preserving nature for future generations. Ability and skills to study nature and its protection. A retrospective analysis of environmental education was combined with the study of modern pedagogical practice, with experimental testing of various forms of environmental education, and data from a survey of experts, which made it possible not only to assess the state, but also to identify objective trends in the development of environmental education of schoolchildren [1]:

– along with the development of traditional forms of environmental education and upbringing, new forms of environmental education are used: film lectures on nature protection, role-playing and situational games, school-wide councils on nature protection, environmental workshops;

– the significance of mass media appears in environmental education and education of students, this process becomes pedagogically balanced.

The main criteria for the effectiveness of mass forms are the broad participation of schoolchildren in environmental protection activities, discipline and order, and the degree of activity. They can be identified by systematic observation and accumulation of material. The criterion for the effectiveness of group forms of environmental education is, first of all, the stability of the composition of the club, circle, section, and the achievement of collective success. Here, much determines the content and methodology of classes; the success of the team and the public recognition of its merits by others are also important. The conditions for the development of the relationship between school, family and the public aimed at achieving the goals of environmental education are also defined [2].

Today, education in the world is considered a priority area of education and upbringing of children. The planet Earth is our common home, and every person living in it should treat it with care and care, preserving all its values and riches. Environmental education is a new direction, one of the priority pedagogical problems is the formation of an ecological culture of children, and this is possible only if the idea of continuous environmental education and upbringing is implemented, which can be ensured by creating a certain system. Environmental education contributes to the upbringing of children with intellectual disabilities by various means of a correct attitude to the

environment, to nature and to themselves, which later becomes the core and indicator of the child's moral upbringing. One of the tasks of environmental education for children with acute viral diseases is the development of the emotional sphere. The work on the formation of environmental awareness in children with intellectual disabilities is carried out by teachers on a daily, continuous basis and covers all areas of activity. Children with disabilities experience the world with an open heart and soul. Much depends on the teachers: how they will relate to nature, whether they will be able to perceive themselves as part of the ecological system. Therefore, one of the main tasks in the work is to familiarize children with their native nature, the formation of ecological culture [3].

The problem of environmental education acquires new characteristics and, accordingly, new approaches to its solution as an integral part of the integral process of social adaptation, life self-determination and personal development of pupils. The process of environmental education manifests itself in various spheres of children's activity in work, in classes, in experiments, in games, namely, in satisfying children's curiosity and in involving the child in the active development of the surrounding world, environmental education is carried out through the entire pedagogical process [4]. Creating conditions is one of the solutions to these problems. A living area has been created where we study houseplants, share our experience in caring for houseplants, and how to properly feed the fish that live in the aquarium. The calendar of observation of objects and phenomena of nature is designed, the seasons are presented with a tear-off calendar, tearing off a calendar sheet every day, children learn to memorize the sequence of days of the week and seasons in a direct form. One of the most important conditions for environmental education is a conversation. The conversation should be short, sufficiently informative, interesting, and diverse. Otherwise, daily moralizing will quickly become boring for students and will not bring any benefit [5].

During the conversation, it is necessary to evoke an emotional response in the soul of the pupil. Children should express their feelings about what they saw - a broken tree, scattered garbage, a bouquet of flowers torn down and thrown, grass set on fire, a beautiful landscape, a blooming flower, birdsong. During walks, excursions, and conversations with children in an informal setting, the teacher instills in them the basic concepts and rules of behavior in nature, justifying and explaining them, and confirming them with concrete examples. The structural component of the walk is: observations, didactic tasks, work activities, outdoor games and exercises. Outdoor games of a natural science nature are associated with imitating the habits of animals, their way of life. Imitating actions, imitating sounds, children consolidate knowledge; the joy obtained during the game contributes to the deepening of interest in nature [6]. Education of ecological culture can be traced in such subject courses as reading and speech development, speech development based on the study of objects and phenomena of the surrounding reality. One of the conditions for successful education of humane feelings is a constant reference to natural science topics, therefore, the program material includes works that contribute to the education of moral and environmental culture of schoolchildren. Reading these works, children experience the feelings of animal characters, their actions and activities. The teacher in the classroom is not so much an informant as an accomplice, an inspirer, who can not only lead, but also have the ability to sympathize and empathize. Thus, it implements the student's resources hidden in the subconscious [7].

All classes should be conducted in a playful way. The game also causes emotional and creative activity in the most complex children. For a child with disabilities, extracurricular

activities are very important, first of all, an effective method for developing creative potential, emotional and volitional sphere, intelligence and psyche. One of the largest forms of work is holding thematic holidays on an ecological theme: "Autumn, autumn, we ask you to visit", "Day of Birds", "Day of Earth, Water and Sun", etc.

Children, with great pleasure, are involved in the organization of holidays: they learn poems, draw drawings, stage skits. All this ultimately contributes to the formation of the child's personality, the development of their abilities, the determination of life prospects and environmental education [8].

Participation in environmental contests, quizzes, drawings, crafts. Making crafts and drawings it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that children see the beauty of their native nature.

Much attention should be paid to observing changes in nature. So that children can see the obvious changes and enjoy the first rain, snow, and the first leaf.

Subbotniks for cleaning the territory, thematic excursions, role-playing games, meetings with interesting people are also of great importance for the education of ecological culture. We also work on environmental education in close cooperation with the families of our students. Only by relying on the family, we can jointly solve the main task-raising a person who is environmentally literate. When working with parents on environmental education of children, we use both traditional forms: parental consultations, conversations, meetings, and non-traditional ones (business games "Nature Experts", "Nature and us"; round table "Education of kindness to nature", discussions "Experimenting and developing", "Ecology and entertaining experiments". Another form of work with the family is educational screens, where we give parents practical advice on a specific topic ("Walking is a source of thought"). Through screens, we introduce children and parents to folk signs, but always with tasks: why do they say that? Such forms of work provide an opportunity to demonstrate to parents what knowledge about nature children have, to show that this knowledge is necessary for the formation of the foundations of ecological culture [9].

Solving the problems of environmental education of children, first of all, form a system of knowledge about nature, teach them to understand and establish existing connections and dependencies in it, and act in accordance with the knowledge gained.

Introducing children to nature is a great lesson - developing children's minds, feelings, stimulating creativity. Having understood the peculiarities of the child's relationship with nature, we develop the best human traits in him, so that through emotions and feelings, we can feed his mind and heart with living knowledge [10].

Thus, we conclude that the formation of an ecological culture is important for the comprehensive development of children with intellectual disabilities.

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